

An Appraisal Model of Ideology and Power in Donald Trump's Inaugural Speech

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Abstract- This study aims to explore categories of linguistic choices in Trump's Inaugural Speech that mirror ideological stance and power relations within political discourse. The study employs a mixed quantitative-qualitative research approach, drawing on Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) and the Appraisal Framework to analyze how Trump's speech constructs and reinforces ideological stances and power relations through linguistic choices. Appraisal Theory (AT) provides a robust framework for examining resources related to attitudes (affect, judgement, appreciation), engagement strategies (dialogic contraction/expansion), and graduation mechanisms (force/focus). By examining these resources, the study reveals how Trump strategically uses persuasive language to mobilize support, assert authority, and frame political narratives. Findings indicate that Trump's persuasive language, characterized by direct address and analyzed using the Appraisal Model, is influential and powerful in capturing the attention and approval of the American public for his political victory. Future research could further explore his ideological stance and power relations by utilizing digitalization techniques in a more modern context.

Keywords: Appraisal framework, ideological stance, power, Trump's Inaugural Speech, political discourse

I. Chapter One Introduction

This chapter highlights three crucial parts: research background, aim and objectives, and research questions.

1.1 Research Background

The kinds of public speaking, political speeches are powerful and influential tools for ideological persuasion, shaping public opinion through rhetorical strategies (Fairclough, 2003; van Dijk, 2008). In particular, inaugural addresses serve as foundational texts for a presidency, establishing policy agendas and legitimizing authority (Charteris-Black, 2014). Donald Trump's 2017 inaugural speech was notable for its assertive tone, nationalist rhetoric, and populist. Political speeches are powerful tools for ideological persuasion, shaping public opinion through rhetorical strategies (Fairclough, 2003; van Dijk, 2008). Inaugural addresses, in particular, serve as foundational texts for a presidency, establishing policy agendas and legitimizing authority (Charteris-Black, 2014). Donald Trump's 2017 inaugural speech was notable for its assertive tone, nationalist rhetoric, and populist appeals, making it a rich case study for analyzing how language constructs power and ideology (Jaworski & Coupland, 2014).

The Appraisal Framework (Martin & White, 2005), an extension of SFL, provides a systematic method for analyzing evaluative language in discourse. Researchers can uncover how speakers negotiate social relationships and persuade audiences by examining attitude (emotional responses), engagement (dialogic positioning), and graduation (intensification) (Hood, 2010). This study employs Appraisal Theory to examine how Trump's use of linguistic choices reflects and reinforce ideological power dynamics. This study aligns with the primary aim, objective and follow-up research questions.

Aim and Objectives Aim

To explore categorizes of linguistic choices in Trump's speech mirroring ideological stance and power relations to political discourse persuasive in grasping the attention and applause of the American public for achieving his political goals.

Objectives

To explore the categorizes of Trump's linguistic choices in his speech.
To examine how these linguistic choices mirror ideological and power relations to political discourse persuasive in grasping the attention and applause of the American public for achieving his political goals.

Questions

What categories of linguistic choices are found in Trump's inaugural speech?
How do these choices mirror ideological stance and power relation to political discourse persuasive in grasping the attention and applause of American public for achieving his political goals?

II. Chapter Two Literature Review

This chapter underscores two crucial parts: the literature of Related Research and previous studies in political discourse through AT.

Literature of Related Research

In this section, we will present three essential parts: an overview of AT, development of AT, and a synthesis of AT.

Overview of Appraisal Theory (AT)

Appraisal Theory (AT) is a robust framework for allowing us to understand how individuals evaluate, interpret, and respond to experiences, events, or stimuli. AT has been a significant area of interest in the fields of linguistics, psychology, and communication. AT primarily examines how speakers express their attitudes, emotions, and evaluations of things, events, and people in communication. In the field of linguistics, AT mainly links to Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) pioneered by M.A.K Halliday, where it provides a linguistic analysis of how emotions, judgements, and evaluations are conveyed through language.

Development of Appraisal Theory (AT)

Appraisal Theory (AT) was initially conceptualized by James R. Martin and Peter P. White in the 1990s, as part of their broader work on Systemic Functional Linguistics. Martin and White defined appraisal as a system of analyzing the ways in which writers or speakers use language to express attitudes, feelings, and assessments affecting emotional tone of a text or discourse.

AT developed by J.R. Martin and others, extends Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) by focusing on the interpersonal function of language at the lexico-grammatical level. It provides a framework for analyzing how speakers or writers convey attitudes, judgments, and appreciations through language, thereby constructing and negotiating power relations in political discourse.

Synthesis of Appraisal Theory (AT)

This theory is built on three main components: attitudes, engagement, and graduation. The first component, attitude evaluates feelings or emotions, such as appreciation (good, fine, fair, etc.), judgement (positive, negative view), or affect (I like, prefer, love, hate, etc.). The second component, engagement refers to how speakers include or exclude alternative voices or perspectives (e.g., acknowledging or silencing other opinions). In spoken discourse like public speaking, engagement is mostly monologic. The third component, graduation adjusts the intensity or focus of an evaluation, either intensifying or diminishing the evaluation.

Previous Studies in Discourse Analysis and Political Communication through Appraisal Approach Appraisal Theory in Discourse Analysis Prior research based on the framework of Appraisal Theory (AT) has applied it to a variety of contexts, including education, political discourse and media communication. For example,

White (2003) analyzed how new articles use language to subtly align readers with attitudes, often through the use of implicit evaluations, adopting appraisal theory. In 2010, Hunston demonstrated how teachers use appraisal to guide students' emotional responses in learning.

Appraisal Theory in Political Communication

The Appraisal Framework has been widely used to analyze evaluative language in political speeches (e.g., Martin & White, 2005; Bednarek, 2006). Studies show that politicians employ affective language to evoke emotions, judgmental terms to assess character, and appreciative expressions to evaluate policies (Wang, 2010). For instance, Charteris-Black (2014) analyzed metaphorical framing in Trump's speeches, revealing how "war" and "battle" metaphors construct an us vs. them ideology. In 2014, Jaworski and Coupland highlighted Trump's use of persuasive strategies such as repetition, hyperbole, and direct address to assert dominance. In 2017, Wilson examined Trump's "America First" discourse, arguing that it reflects neoliberal nationalism and anti-globalist sentiment. Similarly, Lakoff (2016) noted Trump's reliance on "strict father" morality to appeal to conservative voters.

Commonly, inaugural addresses are key sites for ideological projection (Wodak, 2015). Fairclough (2003) emphasized how lexical choices and grammatical structures shape political realities. For example, Obama's 2009 inaugural speech used inclusive language to promote unity, whereas Trump's 2017 speech emphasized division and restoration (Kendall-Taylor & Frantz, 2016).

While previous studies have analyzed politicians' rhetorical style, especially, Donald Trump's, few have applied Appraisal Theory to his inaugural speech specifically. This study fills this gap, addressing a fine-grained analysis of how Trump's evaluative language constructs power and ideology in this pivotal moment of U.S. politics.

III. Chapter Three Methodology

This study employs a mixed-methods research approach. The overarching goal of the study is to explore and categorize linguistic choices in Trump's Inaugural Speech mirroring ideological stance and power relations to political discourse persuasive in grasping the attention and applause of the American public for achieving his political goal within the critical framework of Appraisal Theory (Martin & White, the 1990s). Under this framework, the study highlights three major parts (attitudes, engagement, and graduation) while analyzing Trump's language in his address.

Through quantitative analysis, Trump's linguistic choices will be analyzed using a systematic coding scheme, alongside close reading, which will serve as a fundamental analysis strategy within the Appraisal Theory (AT) framework. Meanwhile, the qualitative analysis focuses on a grounded examination of Trump's speech, drawing on quantitative data to explore the three primary components of linguistic evaluation (attitudes, engagement, and graduation). This underscores how Trump's linguistic choices convey ideological stances and power relations within political discourse, aiming to attract audience attention and achieve political goals. This methodological rigor ultimately bridges linguistic theory and political discourse, emphasizing a holistic understanding of linguistics, psychology, and politics.

IV. Chapter Four Findings and Discussion

This chapter reports all findings of the present study along with relevant discussion.

Categories of Linguistic Choices Found in Trump's inaugural speech aligned with Appraisal Model (RQ1: What categories of linguistic choices are found in Trump's inaugural speech?)

Table 4.1 Attitudes reflecting in Trump's Persuasive Language in his Inaugural Speech

No	Text Segment	Affect	Judgement	Appreciation
1.	We will face challenges. We	Determination,	Resolute,	-
	will confront hardships, but we	Confidence (+)	Effective	
	will get the job done.		(+)	
2.	We are transferring power	Empowerment,	Just,	-
	from Washington, D.C., and	Inclusivity (+)	Fair (+)	
	giving it back to you, the			
	people.			
3.	For too long, a small group in	Discontent,	Injustice,	-
	our nation's capital has reaped	Resentment (-)	Unfair (-)	
	the rewards of government.			
4.	Politicians prospered, but the	Disappointment,	Ineffective,	-
	jobs left and the factories	Anger (-)	Corrupt (-)	
	closed.			
5.	That all changes starting right	Determination,	Resolute,	-
	here and right now because	Confidence (+)	Effective	
	this moment is your moment.		(+)	
6.	January 20th, 2017, will be	Determination,	Resolute,	-
	remembered as the day the	Confidence (+)	Effective	
	people became the rulers of		(+)	
	this nation again.			

7. Americans want great schools	Determination,	Resolute,	-
for their children, safe	Confidence (+)	Effective	
neighborhoods for their		(+)	
families, and good jobs for			
themselves.			

8. Mothers and children trapped in poverty in our inner cities, rusted out factories scattered like tombstones across the landscape of our nation.	Discontent, Resentment (-)	Injustice, Unfair (-)	-
9. Their dreams are our dreams and their success will be our success.	Confidence (+)	Resolute, Effective (+)	-
10. We've defended other nations' borders, while refusing to defend our own, and spent trillions and trillions of dollars overseas.	Disappointment, Anger (-)	Injustice, Unfair (-)	-
11. We've made other countries rich while the wealth, strength and confidence of our country, has dissipated over the horizon.	Disappointment, Anger (-)	Injustice, Unfair (-)	-
12. We assembled here today, are issuing a new decree to be heard in every city, in every foreign capital, and in every hall of power.	Determination, Confidence (+)	Resolute, Effective (+)	-
13. Every decision on trade, on taxes, on immigration, on foreign affairs will be made to benefit American workers and	Determination, Confidence (+)	Resolute, Effective (+)	-

American families.			
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Table 4.2 Engagement embedded in Trump’s Persuasive Language in his Inaugural Speech

14. I will fight for you with every breath in my body and I will never, ever let you down.	Determination, Confidence (+)	Resolute, Effective (+)	-
15. We will get back to work rebuilding our country with American hands and American labor.	Determination, Confidence (+)	Resolute, Effective (+)	-
16. When you open your heart to patriotism, there is no room for prejudice.	Motivation, Confidence (+)	Resolute, Effective (+)	-
17. No challenge can match the heart and fight and spirit of America. We will not fail.	Motivation, Confidence (+)	Resolute, Effective (+)	-
18. We all bleed the same red blood of patriots, whether we are black or brown or white.	Motivation, Confidence (+)	Resolute, Effective (+)	-

No Text Segment Dialogic Contraction

Dialogic Expansion

We will face challenges. We will confront hardships, but we will get the job done.
 We are transferring power from Washington, D.C., and giving it back to you, the people.
 For too long, a small group in our nation’s capital has reaped the rewards of government.
 Politicians prospered, but the jobs left and the factories closed.

- Assert (+) -
- Proclaim (+) -
- Counter (-) -
- Counter (-) -

5. That all changes starting right here and right	Proclaim (+)		-
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now because this moment is your moment.		
6. January 20th, 2017, will be remembered as the day the people became the rulers of this nation again.	Proclaim (+)	-
7. Americans want great schools for their children, safe neighborhoods for their families, and good jobs for themselves.	Counter (-)	-
8. Mothers and children trapped in poverty in our inner cities, rusted out factories scattered like tombstones across the landscape of our nation.	Counter (-)	-
9. Their dreams are our dreams and their success will be our success.	Assert (+)	-
10. We've defended other nations' borders, while refusing to defend our own, and spent trillions and trillions of dollars overseas.	Counter (-)	-
11. We've made other countries rich while the wealth, strength and confidence of our country, has dissipated over the horizon.	Counter (-)	-
12. We assembled here today, are issuing a new decree to be heard in every city, in every foreign capital, and in every hall of power.	Assert (+)	-
13. Every decision on trade, on taxes, on immigration, on foreign affairs will be made to benefit American workers and American families.	Assert (+)	-
14. I will fight for you with every breath in my	Assert (+)	-

body and I will never, ever let you down.		
15. We will get back to work rebuilding our country with American hands and American labor.	Assert (+)	-

When you open your heart to patriotism, there is no room for prejudice.
 No challenge can match the heart and fight and spirit of America. We will not fail.
 We all bleed the same red blood of patriots, whether we are black or brown or white.
 Assert (+) -
 Assert (+) -
 Assert (+) -

Table 4.3 Graduation embedded in Trump’s Persuasive Language in his Inaugural Speech

No	Text Segment	Force	Focus
1.	We will face challenges. We will	Strong	
	confront hardships, but we will get the job done.	Commitment (+)	
2.	We are transferring power from		Complete transfer
	Washington, D.C., and giving it back to you, the people.		(+)
3.	For too long, a small group in our		A small group
	nation’s capital has reaped the rewards of government.		(limited) (-)
4.	Politicians prospered, but the jobs		Factories (Loss) (-)
	left and the factories closed.		
5.	That all changes starting right here and right now because this moment is your moment.	Proclaim (+)	-
6.	January 20th, 2017, will be remembered as the day the people became the rulers of this nation again.	Proclaim (+)	-
7.	Americans want great schools for their children, safe neighborhoods for their families, and good jobs for themselves.	Counter (-)	-

8. Mothers and children trapped in poverty in our inner cities, rusted out factories scattered like tombstones across the landscape of our nation.	Counter (-)	-
9. Their dreams are our dreams and their success will be our success.	Assert (+)	-
10. We've defended other nations' borders, while refusing to defend our own, and spent trillions and trillions of dollars overseas.	Counter (-)	-
11. We've made other countries rich while the wealth, strength and confidence of our country, has dissipated over the horizon.	Counter (-)	-
12. We assembled here today, are issuing a new decree to be heard in every city, in every foreign capital, and in every hall of power.	Assert (+)	-
13. Every decision on trade, on taxes, on immigration, on foreign affairs will be made to benefit American workers and American families.	Assert (+)	-
14. I will fight for you with every breath in my body and I will never, ever let you down.	Assert (+)	-
15. We will get back to work rebuilding our country with American hands and American labor.	Assert (+)	-
16. When you open your heart to patriotism, there is no room for prejudice.	Assert (+)	
17. No challenge can match the heart and fight and spirit of America. We will not fail.	Assert (+)	
18. We all bleed the same red blood of patriots, whether we are black or brown or white.	Assert (+)	

Donald Trump employed persuasive linguistic choices in his inaugural speech as shown above in three tables. Here, we will evaluate how Trump's language is persuasive in grasping the applause and attention of American public, extracting some important facts shown in the above tables.

By means of Table 4.1, Trump used positive affect and positive judgement prominently more than other facts in his speech. His determination and confidence positively contributed to the affect on most of the facts such as "We will face challenges. We will confront hardships, but we will get the job done" while his resolute and effective judgement on these facts convey his positive judgement. Some of his facts like "We are transferring power from Washington, D.C., and giving it back to you, the people" brought a positive attitude to the political discourse. However, Trump had a negative attitude on actions of former government, the poverty of American citizens, the decrease of national economic strength and the increase of jobless people in the whole country. But there was neither positive nor negative attitude on appreciation.

In accordance with Table 4.2, Trump had positive engagement on the facts that he asserts and proclaims in most of the cases (I will fight for you with every breath in my body and I will never, ever let you down, January 20th, 2017, will be remembered as the day the people became the rulers of this nation again etc.). However, he had the negative judgement on some facts like "Politicians prospered, but the jobs left and the factories closed."

Based on Table 4.3, in the sector of graduation, he had positive forces and focus. For instance, he had positive forces (Strong Commitments) in some facts like "We will get back to work rebuilding our country with American hands and American labor" while he had also positive focus (Complete transfer) in some facts like "We are transferring power from Washington, D.C., and giving it back to you, the people."

In conclusion, Trump's linguistic choices can be evaluated in line with the Appraisal Model that his persuasive language has a significant positive attitude, the positive engagement and a positive graduation. Trump's Linguistic Choices mirroring Ideological stance and Power relations to Political Discourse (RQ2: How do these choices mirror ideological stance and power relation to political discourse persuasive in grasping the attention of the American public for achieving his political goals?)

The current leader of the U.S, president Donald Trump employed persuasive and direct address in his inaugural speech. Due to the Appraisal Model, his speech exhibited positive attitudes. In the sector of affect, his affirmative statements (e.g., We will face challenges. We will confront hardships, but we will get the job done.) convey positive attitude due to the determination and confidence expressed in his speech. These statements are very influential to demand the attention and applause of (his audience) the American public.

Additionally, his use of language conveys a positive attitude based on the sector of judgement. For example, he expressed a great attitude towards certain facts, such as "We will get back to work rebuilding our country with American hands and American labor." Besides, these statements maintained a positive judgement, attracting audiences' attention, as these judgements were resolute and effective.

Trump's speech was persuasive in grasping the attention for achieving his political goals in the sector of engagement and graduation. In the sector of engagement, his use of sentence structures like "We will face challenges. We will confront hardships, but we will get the job done" brought about positive engagement as these statements were very assertive. Similarly, his choice of language demonstrated positive judgement on certain facts like "We are transferring power from Washington, D.C., and giving it back to you, the people" as these statements showed his proclaims.

In the sector of graduation, Trump's speech bore positive forces and focuses. For example, his choices of language (e.g., Their dreams are our dreams and their success will be our success) showed his strong

commitment while some facts (e.g., We've made other countries rich while the wealth, strength and confidence of our country, has dissipated over the horizon.) proved his resentment and disappointment.

In conclusion, Trump's linguistic choices such as lexical and grammatical selection are directive and persuasive in grasping the attention and applause of the American public for achieving his political goals.

Discussion Trump's Linguistic Choices reflecting ideology and power to Political Discourse

While previous studies have analyzed politicians' rhetorical style, especially, few have applied Appraisal Theory to Trump's inaugural speech specifically. In 2014, Jaworski and Coupland Donald Trump's use of persuasive strategies such as repetition, hyperbole, and direct address to assert dominance. In the same year, Charteris-Black analyzed metaphorical framing in Trump's speeches, revealing how "war" and "battle" metaphors construct an us vs. them ideology. In 2016, Kendall-Taylor and Frantz analyzed Trump's 2017 speech, emphasizing division and restoration. In 2017, Wilson examined Trump's "America First" discourse, arguing that it reflects neoliberal nationalism and anti-globalist sentiment.

The present study endeavoured to conduct a fine-grained analysis of how Trump's evaluative language constructs power and ideology in this pivotal moment of U.S. politics. The study examined Trump's persuasive language within the critical framework of Appraisal Model, utilizing a close reading technique by adopting the mixed method. Based on quantitative data across a systemic coding scheme, Trump employed his direct language in his inaugural speech. His affirmative statements, such as "We will face challenges. We will confront hardships, but we will get the job done" demonstrated his determined and confident affect while showing his resolute and effective judgement, which highlights his positive attitude. Similarly, this statement (Trump's assertive dialogue) proved his positive engagement and his positive force (strong commitment) highlighting his refined graduation. The findings of this study ultimately address the gap of the prior research which lacked the evaluation on Trump's language used in his inaugural speech reflecting ideological stance and power relations to political discourse.

V. Chapter Five Conclusion

This study investigated the ideological stances and power relations in political discourse in Trump's inaugural speech, drawing on the Appraisal Model. The study employed a mixed-method approach. Through quantitative analysis, Trump's use of linguistic choices was analyzed across a systemic coding scheme. According to the component of attitude, his positive attitude was evident in affect and judgement. Similarly, according to the components of engagement and graduation, his speech centred on a positive view. Through qualitative analysis, these data were analyzed in-depth to understand how they could influence the audience's attention for achieving his political goals. Findings reveal that Trump's linguistic choices are influential and powerful in captivating the attention and approval of the American public for his political victory. Future research could explore his ideological stance and power relations further, incorporating digitalization in a more modern era.

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